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MONITORING STUDENT ATTENDANCE USING A SMART SYSTEM AT TAIF UNIVERSITY

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ABSTRACT

This Children are future of a society within a country. They should be provided with all round educational development since educating children has many advantages. If they are educated, they can face any problem and this makes them strong and happy. In other words the growth of a country is dependent on its learned population. Children with special education needs have problems to develop cognitive abilities like thinking, learning and obtain new knowledge and concept. It may also be required to improve their conduct, communication skills and interactions with their environment. It is required to develop customizable and compliant applications designed to support them in adapting with respect to the current situations they face and thus take actions appropriately. Such applications would provide them the assistance to allow them frame their learning essentials and help to process to the diverse sensory and cognitive impairments including the mobility issues. This research will be based on artificial intelligence concept and will be self-adaptable. Besides, in many cases they have the opportunity to perform activities that previously were not accessible to them, because of the interface and contents of the activities have been adapted specifically to them. The study also suggests that the repertoire of types of activities provided is suitable for learning purposes with students with impairments. Finally, the use of electronic devices and multimedia contents increases their interest in learning and attention

KEYWORDS

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A STUDY ON COFFEE PRODUCT CATEGORIES SOLD IN LANDSCAPE COFFEE SHOPS

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ABSTRACT

Regarding delicacies, people are no longer satisfied with mere good taste, they also consider the overall feeling conveyed by the restaurants, including the decorations, the created atmosphere, and services, which all affect consumers' decisions whether dine. Nowadays, casual style is particularly the leading trend. Modern restaurants have innovative ideas in food, leisure, and consumption, which are different from traditional restaurants that only meet customers' needs for daily meals. Therefore, many featured restaurants are opened with unique styles to attract consumers. This study investigated the decision-making processes for coffee product categories sold in the landscape coffee shops. The landscape coffee shops in Taiwan all have unique featured services and functions to attract consumers. The quality of coffee products sold in the landscape coffee shops is one of the factors that consumers consider, and is the key to sustainable operation of coffee shops. As the preference of consumers varies, this study used analytic hierarchy process (AHP) to investigate the coffee tastes of most consumers, allowing landscape coffee shops to focus on the popular coffee product in order to achieve sustainable operation. Based on the results of literature review, expert interviews, and AHP, this study provides useful suggestions to landscape coffee shops.

KEYWORDS

Landscape Coffee Shops, Analytic Hierarchy Process, Coffee Beans

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SMART MOTORCYCLE HELMET: REAL-TIME CRASH DETECTION WITH EMERGENCY NOTIFICATION, TRACKER AND ANTI-THEFT SYSTEM USING INTERNET-OF-THINGS CLOUD BASED TECHNOLOGY

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ABSTRACT

Buying a car entails a cost, not counting the day to day high price tag of gasoline. People are looking for viable means of transportation that is cost-effective and can move its way through traffic faster. In the Philippines, motorcycle was the answer to most people transportation needs. With the increasing number of a motorcycle rider in the Philippines safety is the utmost concern. Today technology plays a huge role on how this safety can be assured. We now see advances in connected devices. Devices can sense its surrounding through sensor attach to it. With this in mind, this study focuses on the development of a wearable device named Smart Motorcycle Helmet or simply Smart Helmet, whose main objective is to help motorcycle rider in times of emergency. Utilizing sensors such as alcohol level detector, crash/impact sensor, Internet connection thru 3G, accelerometer, Short Message Service (SMS) and cloud computing infrastructure connected to a Raspberry Pi Zero-W and integrating a separate Arduino board for the anti-theft tracking module is used to develop the propose Internet-of Things (IoT) device.

Using quantitative method and descriptive type research, the researchers validated the results from the inputs of the participant who tested the smart helmet during the alpha and beta testing process. Taking into account the ethical consideration of the volunteers, who will test the Smart Helmet. To ensure the reliability of the beta and alpha testing, ISO 25010 quality model was used for the assessment focusing on the device accuracy, efficiency and functionality. Based on the inputs and results gathered, the proposed Smart Helmet IoT device can be used as a tool in helping a motorcycle rider when an accident happens to inform the first-responder of the accident location and informing the family of the motorcycle rider.

KEYWORDS

Smart Helmet, Internet of Things, Sensors, Real-Time Crash Detection, Emergency Notification, Tracker, Anti-Theft System Cloud Based Technology

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COMPLETE END-TO-END LOW COST SOLUTION TO A 3D SCANNING SYSTEM WITH INTEGRATED

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ABSTRACT

3D reconstruction is a technique used in computer vision which has a wide range of applications in areas like object recognition, city modelling, virtual reality, physical simulations, video games and special effects. Previously, to perform a 3D reconstruction, specialized hardwares were required. Such systems were often very expensive and was only available for industrial or research purpose. With the rise of the availability of high-quality low cost 3D sensors, it is now possible to design inexpensive complete 3D scanning systems. The objective of this work was to design an acquisition and processing system that can perform 3D scanning and reconstruction of objects seamlessly. In addition, the goal of this work also included making the 3D scanning process fully automated by building and integrating a turntable alongside the software. This means the user can perform a full 3D scan only by a press of a few buttons from our dedicated graphical user interface. Three main steps were followed to go from acquisition of point clouds to the finished reconstructed 3D model. First, our system acquires point cloud data of a person/object using inexpensive camera sensor. Second, align and convert the acquired point cloud data into a watertight mesh of good quality. Third, export the reconstructed model to a 3D printer to obtain a proper 3D print of the model.

KEYWORDS

3D Body Scanning, 3D Printing, 3D Reconstruction, Iterative Closest Process, Automated Scanning System, Kinect v2.0 Sensor, RGB-D camera, Point Cloud Library (PCL)

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AN EXPLORATION OF THE FACTORS AFFECTING USERS' SATISFACTION WITH MOBILE PAYMENTS

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ABSTRACT

Mobile payment allows consumers to make more flexible payments through convenient mobile devices. While mobile payment is easy and time save, the operation and security of mobile payment must ensure that the payment is fast, convenient, reliable and safety in order to increase the users' satisfaction. Therefore, this study based on technology acceptance model to explore the impact of external variables through perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use on users' satisfaction. The data analysis methods used in this study are descriptive statistical analysis, reliability and validity analysis, Pearson correlation analysis and regression analysis to verify the hypotheses. The results show that all hypotheses are supported. However, mobile payment is still subject to many restrictions on development and there are limited related researches. The results of this study provided insight into the factors that affect the users' satisfaction for mobile payment. Related services development of mobile payment and future research suggestions are also offered.

KEYWORDS

Mobile Payment, Technology Acceptance Model, Users' satisfaction

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DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION OF A RASPBERRY-PI BASED HOME SECURITY AND FIRE SAFETY SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

Fire alarms and building security systems are currently separate systems and are liable to monthly fees. Video recording for closed-circuit television (CCTV) is done locally subsequently requiring high storage space. Whenever there is a break-in, the footage records can be stolen consequently losing data. To address high data storage space, monthly premium subscriptions, cost of separate systems and data loss issues of the aforementioned systems, we design and implement a Raspberry-pi based fire and intrusion detection systems in this work. The system sends an SMS in the case of an intrusion or fire detection, and then records and uploads the surveillance videos. The system used a GSM modem for sending SMSs, a video, a PIR sensor to detect motion and a smoke or heat sensor to detect fire. The system is a low cost combined home security and fire detection Raspberry-pi system intended for home and small offices use.

KEYWORDS

Raspberry-Pi, PIR, GSM, Security ,

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AN ALGORITHM FOR PREDICTIVE DATA MINING APPROACH IN MEDICAL DIAGNOSIS

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ABSTRACT

The Healthcare industry contains big and complex data that may be required in order to discover fascinating pattern of diseases & makes effective decisions with the help of different machine learning techniques. Advanced data mining techniques are used to discover knowledge in database and for medical research. This paper has analyzed prediction systems for Diabetes, Kidney and Liver disease using more number of input attributes. The data mining classification techniques, namely Support Vector Machine(SVM) and Random Forest (RF) are analyzed on Diabetes, Kidney and Liver disease database. The performance of these techniques is compared, based on precision, recall, accuracy, f_measure as well as time. As a result of study the proposed algorithm is designed using SVM and RF algorithm and the experimental result shows the accuracy of 99.35%, 99.37 and 99.14 on diabetes, kidney and liver disease respectively. Finally, we propose recommendations for improving security, and mitigating risks encounter virtualization that necessary to adopt secure cloud computing.

KEYWORDS

Data Mining, Clinical Decision Support System, Disease Prediction, Classification, SVM, RF.

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A SURVEY ON SECURITY CHALLENGES OF VIRTUALIZATION TECHNOLOGY IN CLOUD COMPUTING

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ABSTRACT

Virtualization has become a widely and attractive employed technology in cloud computing environments. Sharing of a single physical machine between multiple isolated virtual machines leading to a more optimized hardware usage, as well as make the migration and management of a virtual system more efficiently than its physical counterpart. Virtualization is a fundamental technology in a cloud environment. However, the presence of an additional abstraction layer among software and hardware causes new security issues. Security issues related to virtualization technology have become a significant concern for organizations due to arising some new security challenges.

This paper aims to identify the main challenges and risks of virtualization in cloud computing environments. Furthermore, it focuses on some common virtual-related threats and attacks affect the security of cloud computing.

The survey was conducted to obtain the views of the cloud stakeholders on virtualization vulnerabilities, threats, and approaches that can be used to overcome them.

Finally, we propose recommendations for improving security, and mitigating risks encounter virtualization that necessary to adopt secure cloud computing.

KEYWORDS

Cloud Computing, Virtualization, Security, Challenge, Risk

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INTRUSION DETECTION SYSTEM CLASSIFICATION USING DIFFERENT MACHINE LEARNING ALGORITHMS ON KDD-99 AND NSL-KDD DATASETS - A REVIEW PAPER

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ABSTRACT

Intrusion Detection System (IDS) has been an effective way to achieve higher security in detecting malicious activities for the past couple of years. Anomaly detection is an intrusion detection system. Current anomaly detection is often associated with high false alarm rates and only moderate accuracy and detection rates because it's unable to detect all types of attacks correctly. An experiment is carried out to evaluate the performance of the different machine learning algorithms using KDD-99 Cup and NSL-KDD datasets. Results show which approach has performed better in term of accuracy, detection rate with reasonable false alarm rate.

KEYWORDS

Intrusion Detection System, KDD-99 cup, NSL-KDD, Machine learning algorithms.

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COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF FCFS, SJN & RR JOB SCHEDULING ALGORITHMS

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ABSTRACT

One of the primary roles of the operating system is job scheduling. Oftentimes, what makes the difference between the performance of one operating system over the other could be the underlying implementation of its job scheduling algorithm. This paper therefore examines, under identical conditions and parameters, the comparative performances of First Come First Serve (FCFS), Shortest Job Next (SJN) and Round Robin (RR) scheduling algorithms. Simulation results presented in this paper serve to stimulate further research into the subject area.

KEYWORDS

Scheduling; Task; Thread; Process; Algorithm; Operating Systems; Scheduling

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